

1 **Pannexin and purinergic receptor induction during resistance to chemotherapy in triple negative**
2 **breast cancer.**

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7 *P2RX7* was activated, and pannexin 2 was induced. Other purinergic receptors were silenced, including
8 *P2RX2*.

9 Citations

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